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Resistance to TNF inhibition is associated with Arg1 induction.

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We conducted a genome-wide expression screen to identify genes important for resistance to TNF inhibition. We discovered a likely functional role for Arg1 in mediating a component of the resistance response to tumor necrosis factor alpha inhibition in humans.